

RESPONSE PAPER

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PROGRAM CODE : DILT

COURSE CODE : ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: PERIOD 1

INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on MacBook)

GOOD ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I discovered that the import of this course is to know how to write a good essay, the structure of the essay, the writing style to be adopted, the choice of grammar, the recommended referencing style, the ethics of good essay writing and finally the common differences between the American English and the British English. Much as I appreciated the pointers that were reiterated in the study period 1, I found it a bit humbling that I had undertaken a course in essay writing before I could commence my doctoral studies; my ego was a bit bruised with the realization that it was assumed that I had to go back to the basics of essay writing at a doctoral level! Nevertheless, for me it was a curious, but rather boring experience.

2) ESSAY WRITING

The key to a good essay writing starts with the analysis of the question and the construction of an initial plan on how to amplify the idea sought to be explicated on (EUCLID 2015, 1-3). To achieve this one must have comprehensively researched the topic, made relevant notes therefrom, and support the argument being rendered with adequate evidence in the form of references where the need arises (EUCLID 2015, 4). It is critical in a good essay to give credit to the source of any information being reproduced and to also avoid plagiarism (EUCLID 2015,5-9), this problem is solved when all authors and sources of any information used are properly cited. The difference between in - text citations, quotations and paraphrasing are explained in the study material (EUCLID 2015, 13-32).

A good writing should be readily understandable; it should not be stuffy, it should neither be arrogant, nor should it be boastful, it should not be didactic, and it should be lucid (The Style Guide, 1998, 1-3). I have attempted to follow most of these basic rules in the course of the few academic and semi-academic articles I have written in my career. The study pack amplifies most of these norms and suggests a few more which all aid the production of a more efficient academic article.

The basic rules for a good paper are emphasized with the student being urged to state the main thesis, stay focused, to avoid leading and concluding with generalities and to write clearly and seriously (EUCLID 2015, 42-43). As a litigation lawyer, this is familiar territory for me as court briefs take the same format and are guided by similar rules.

3) STYLES

The Chicago Rules (Turabian) is the style recommended for use by the students in any form of academic writing at EUCLID, and the student is advised on the importance of strict adherence to this directive. I am bit puzzled with why academic writing has to be strictly in this style or any other style for that matter to be appreciated. I hold the view that if an essay is clearly, concisely and seriously written in a manner that clearly transfers the writer's opinions and ideas to the reader it should suffice, as long as it respects all the rules of plagiarism and good grammar.

I think that it is rather stifling and restrictive to insist that an essay must be in the Turabian style or any other approved style before it can meet the basis for presentation; especially for doctoral students whom would have been exposed to academic writing at one stage or the other of their academic and/or professional endeavors. Hence, I feel that the focus on particularized writing styles is being overemphasized and good, and effective academic writing ought to be sufficient.

The admonishment that "The moral for editors is that they should respect good writing." seems to lend itself to my position (The Economist Newspaper Ltd., Style Guide, 1998, 4). I feel writing should reflect the writer's personality, his mindset and his attitude to the topic which is the subject matter of the article and as long as he expresses such views in a way that is simple to read, it should be encouraged; and insistence on a particularized style may in the end make the article look and come across like a textbook which may in the end discourage large readership.

I must confess that due to my prejudices against having to conform to a particularized style in order to have an academic article deemed "worthy" made this area of the study pack a bit unwieldy and a hard read for me.

4) CONCLUSION

In the course of going through the study pack, the section dealing with the structure, the content and the way to write a good essay were quite helpful, as it is practical and one can see how the application of it to any paper I write, be it in the university here or for court purposes, the aids provided if adhered will make for a better paper. I found the basic differences between American English (SAE) and the British English (SBE), especially as it reflects in pronunciation, spelling, grammar, syntax, punctuation, expressions and most importantly the 'Ethnolects' amplified for a better understanding (EUCLID 2015, 53-56).

The placing of punctuation marks, that is, periods/full stops inside or outside a quotation was an area I had hitherto assumed was primarily based on the writers discretion and not linked to the American or British English styles, though I fail to appreciate the point made with the location of the punctuation mark in or after a quotation, because unlike other features of the distinction of American and English styles for instance the replacement of the word "z" for "s" or the total removal of the word "u" in the American English version that can be linked to practicality of pronunciations, this particular distinction seems more suited to the look than the practicality of English language usage (EUCLID 2015,46-47). The same opinion applies to the use of inverted commas for the British English and the quotation marks for the American English (EUCLID 2015, 58).

I found the portion on personal versus academic writing quite interesting, and learning that I ought not to use contractions such as "can't" and "won't" new (EUCLID 2015, 38), I have previously never understood the difference between the type of writing and situations when they could not be used, and the differences between the meaning of contractions such as "it's" and "its" were novel to me (EUCLID 2015, 46).

I find the need for a style guide over emphasized; much as I hesitate to call myself a creative writer, I feel that with the exception of language style adopted (American or British) there is very little more to the style guide than punctuation, grammar and vocabulary, every other so called consideration only goes to the look of the writing and not really to the substance, for instance I don't see how the font usage and preferred sentence style will affect the depth of the subject being discussed in the article if it is well researched and the basic norms of good academic writing are all followed. The structure, the indentation, the symbols all lend to the aesthetics of the article and not so much more.

I must admit in the end that having to go through this course on good essay writing was both humbling and educational; I realized in the course of going through the study pack that I did not know as much as I had assumed on good essay writing, and writing academic and semi-academic papers frequently did not translate to excellent academic writing. My mind will struggle with the adherence to the strict writing style demanded by the university, other than that, I think I would be fine if not better going forward; besides the course has sobered me up properly for the much more serious work ahead.

REFERENCES

Euclid University. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack Period 1*. Retrieved from the <http://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1> (Accessed in January 2020).

The Style Guide, 5th Edition London: Profile Books Ltd., 1998.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.